

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: REHNBERG****FIRST NAME: STEPHEN****PROGRAM CODE: DCCTh****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did *not* use Grammarly Premium

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: not calculated

The author used the following software: MSWord 2010 on Windows 10

List your 5 key concepts with page number in text:

1. What is An Academic Essay (EUCLID 2021, 7)
2. Punctuation: The Importance of Commas (EUCLID 2021, 15-23)
3. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)
4. It's All About Style (EUCLID 2021, 44)
5. Avoid TLAS-Three Letter Acronyms (EUCLID 2021, 44)

BASIC TOOLS NEEDED FOR WRITING AN ACCEPTABLE ACADEMIC PAPER

1) INTRODUCTION

As eager as I am to begin researching and writing my dissertation for a Doctor in Philosophy (Ph.D.) in Catholic Studies, I understand the need to first acquire the technical skills necessary to write an acceptable scholarly paper. A paper that not only informs its readers but also conforms to the expectations of the academic audience in terms of style, grammar, and authoritative citations in support of my arguments.

This first course in essay writing provides some of the necessary basic tools that I will need to write response papers and, ultimately, my dissertation as I progress through the Ph.D. program at Euclid. While I previously knew some of the information provided in this first course, there were some surprises, notably being able to write a response paper in the first-person singular as opposed to the third-person singular (EUCLID 2021, 14). I have always found it awkward and somewhat cowardly to write “in this paper, the author will demonstrate” instead of “in this paper, I will demonstrate.” After all, I am making the argument, and it should be clear to the reader who to criticize if criticism is warranted.

In this first response paper, I will discuss five major concepts presented in the ACA-401D coursepack for period one: academic essay, punctuation, plagiarism, style guide, abbreviations, and acronyms.

2) WHAT IS AN ACADEMIC ESSAY?

The tenth edition of the Merriam Webster’s Collegiate Dictionary defines an essay as “an analytical or interpretative literary composition usu. dealing with its subject from a limited or personal point of view” (Merriam-Webster 1995, 396). This definition allows for writings based solely on one’s personal observations, thoughts, or opinions to be essays. For example, Henry David Thoreau’s *Walden*, a series of eighteen writings based on his experiences of simple living on Walden Pond near Concord, Massachusetts, from 1845-47, are essays in the literary world (Lowne 2023, webpage). An academic essay differs, however, in that it “seek(s) to provide answer(s) to a hypothesis, aiming to communicate ideas based on evidence” (EUCLID 2021, 7).

The key difference between an academic essay and other writings considered essays is that the author of an academic essay must provide authoritative and independently verifiable evidence in support of their argument(s). The author accomplishes this through citations contained within their essay that indicate the authoritative source(s) from which they base their argument(s) and/or conclusion(s). In general, the format for citations used in an academic essay should include enough information for a reader to verify the veracity of the evidence presented by the essay’s author. This citation information usually consists, at a minimum, of the name(s) of the author(s), year of publication, title of publication, publisher and city where published, or URL if the information was obtained from the internet.

3) PUNCTUATION: THE IMPORTANCE OF COMMAS

In general, commas are used to “surround a non-defining clause (one which adds descriptive information but which can be removed without losing the meaning of the sentence) (EUCLID 2021, 19). Conversely, a defining clause is not set off by commas.

A misplaced or missing comma can completely change the meaning of a sentence. Consider the two sentences with exactly the same wording:

Let’s eat grandma.

Let’s eat, grandma.

The first sentence exhorts the subjects of the sentence, us, to commit cannibalism (eat grandma), while the second sentence requests grandma to partake in a meal with the subjects. The only difference between the two sentences is the careful and necessary placement of a comma, without which the reader is left with an entirely different meaning.

Other proper uses of the comma are to surround a non-defining word or phrase, after an introductory adverb, adverbial phrase (with the exception of a time-based adverbial phrase), a subordinate clause, or between multiple qualitative adjectives (EUCLID 2021, 19).

4) PLAGIARISM

In the simplest terms, plagiarism is stealing! The intentional copying or paraphrasing of another's written work, ideas, or spoken words without acknowledging or giving credit to them and resulting in the reader believing the work, ideas, or spoken words are solely those of the author. Besides being unethical, plagiarism is also unfair to take someone's work and not give them credit, and is a serious academic offense that can result in serious consequences (EUCLID 2021, 34).

To avoid plagiarism, "the solution is to properly CITE the author or source that has provided the information you are using" (EUCLID 2012, 34). My rule of thumb is when in doubt, give credit to the author or source from which you have developed your argument, even if it is in the form of an explanatory footnote. It is far better to give too much credit to a source than to suffer the embarrassment, loss of creditability as a researcher or scholarly writer, and potentially serious consequences of being accused of plagiarism.

5) IT'S ALL ABOUT STYLE

Academic essays and dissertations require that they follow a recognized and accepted format. For response papers and dissertations submitted at Euclid, the suggested and recommended format is the Chicago Style as documented in the "*Chicago Manual of Style* (CMS), 2003, and Kate Turabian's *Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 1996 (EUCLID 2021, 44).

A style guide, such as the Chicago Manual of Style, helps the writer to be consistent in their treatment of in-text citations, footnotes, endnotes, references, and bibliographies. Further, the style guide provides guidance on proper grammar, punctuation, capitalization, abbreviations and acronyms, compound words and hyphenation, italics and quotation marks, numbers used in text, quotations, and page formatting.

6) AVOID TLAS -THREE-LETTER ACRONYMS

Early in my military career, I received a letter that began "UP AR 50-5 and IAW FM 20-15..." I had no idea what this opening sentence meant or even how to interpret what the author wanted to convey. The writer of the letter made the false, perhaps naive, assumption that I would know the abbreviations and acronyms commonly used in military correspondence. The letter's author actually violated a Department of Defense (DOD) directive regarding the use of abbreviations and acronyms. That directive required that

before using an acronym or abbreviation, it must first appear fully written with the abbreviation or acronym immediately following in parentheses such as was done when I wrote Department of Defense (DOD) above. Had the author of the letter followed the DOD directive, the first sentence would have read “Under the Provisions (UP) of Army Regulation (AR) 50-5 and In Accordance With (IAW) Field Manual (FM) 20-15...” My life would have been so much easier, although my company first sergeant would have missed his chance to chuckle at a second lieutenant not conversant in Army speak.

The point to be made is to never introduce an abbreviation or acronym without first fully writing out the abbreviation or acronym. Thereafter, the reader will know what is meant by the abbreviation or acronym if it appears further in the essay. Never assume that the reader of your essay will understand the abbreviation or acronym even if they are common and widely used in your field of study. English may not be the reader’s native language and by not first defining the abbreviation or acronym, you are adding an unnecessary level of complication for the reader to fully understand your essay. In short “abbreviations [and acronyms] should be used only in contexts where they are clear to readers” (words in brackets added) (EUCLID 2021, 44).

7) CONCLUSION

As I begin my academic journey with Euclid University, a journey that I hope and pray will result in a Ph.D. in Catholic Studies, it is important and incumbent upon me to learn and follow the many rules of academic writing. A major step in this direction is to know and understand how to apply the Chicago Manual of Style to my writings in this and the courses to follow. The response papers to be written and submitted in this course and future courses are an excellent way to develop those necessary writing skills.

While some of the information provided in this first course was known to me previously, having been exposed to the Chicago Manual of Style in the writing of my thesis for a Master in Theological Studies, I found this first course to be an excellent refresher. With each subsequent response paper, I hope to experience a seamless integration of the elements of the Chicago Style such that it becomes second nature. Finally, as stated in the introduction, the ability and acceptance of being able to write in the first person singular is welcomed.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabriu Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

Lowne, Cathy. 2023. "Walden." *Encyclopedia Britannica*. Accessed October 8, 2023. <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Walden>.

Merriam-Webster. 1995. *Merriam Webster's Collegiate Dictionary*. Tenth Edition. Springfield: Merriam-Webster, Incorporated.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.